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The Limits Of National Sovereignty: An Analysis Of The Line Between Airspace And Space. Expanding On Space Law And Government (1963) By Andrew G. Haley

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ABSTRACT

Andrew G Haley (19 November 1904 – 11 September 1966) was a renowned American lawyer who was instrumental in the development of modern space law. He and Dr. Theodore von Kármán together formed the Aerojet Engineering Corporation in 1942. Haley's seminal book "Space Law and Government" (1963) was written in the years after Sputnik, at the height of the Cold War, and several years prior to the signing of the Outer Space Treaty. In Chapter Four of his book, Haley recounts the essential arguments for establishing a scientific boundary, governed by the laws of physics and what he saw as the limits of current technology, between airspace and outer space. Haley argues that state sovereignty extends only to the point at which state interest exists, and that wherever space begins, it should not be subject to national jurisdiction. As part of the historical Haley Project, SCF Interns have updated and annotated chapters of his book. In this paper, we examine the arguments Haley made regarding how the law should demarcate between air and space. We note that Haley gives conflicting information regarding the calculation of the von Kármán line and what it is supposed to represent. Despite these ambiguities and subsequent critiques, the von Kármán line, largely through Haley's efforts, has become the prevailing, albeit pseudo-scientific, standard for defining the commencement of outer space in international law and practice.

KEYWORDS: national sovereignty, Karman line, global commons

1. INTRODUCTION

The term “national sovereignty” refers to a State’s independent authority to govern its domestic jurisdiction in accordance with international law. The *1944 Convention on International Civil Aviation* established that a State has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory. By

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the time of his 1963 book “Space Law and Government”, Andrew G. Haley had foreseen the definition of the upper limits of national sovereignty becoming a “first-class problem of international relations.”

Recent developments in private space travel have increased the need for a legal demarcation of the upper limit of sovereignty. Firstly, the number of artificial satellites orbiting the Earth has increased tremendously, and there has been a downward trend in the altitude of those satellites in recent years. This is mostly due to the increased proportion of satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO), which now account for around 84% of orbiting satellites,⁴ which, in turn, is mostly the result of satellite internet providers. Secondly, space is more important in general; there have now been numerous launches even outside of the Earth’s orbit with various countries possessing this ability as opposed to only the USSR and the US, militaries of the world have developed or are actively developing various capabilities to de-orbit objects, and there are now LEO-orbiting Satellites capable of detailed imagery of subjacent nations at a resolution of less than 1 meter.⁵ At that time of Haley’s writing, more than a hundred nations had asserted sovereignty over their superjacent airspace, but not a single one had established where “airspace” ends and “space” begins, treating terms such as “airspace” and “atmosphere” as synonymous. Haley noted that as of 1963, no nation had yet claimed sovereignty above the area of its sovereign “airspace” as set out in the *1927 Paris Convention*⁶ and the *1955 Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention)*.⁷ Haley urged nations to eschew determination of this limit simply by *ex parte* statements and strive for a material definition of the border between sovereign airspace and “space.”

Haley focuses on what he terms the “von Karman jurisdictional line”, named after the famed aerodynamicist Dr. Theodore von Karman, who is ostensibly responsible for its calculation. In a paper delivered in the spring of 1957, Haley showed the below figure of the Karman line superimposed on a diagram made by Masson and Gazley of the Rand Corporation, illustrating the possible ranges for continuous flight in the velocity-altitude coordinate system.

Figure 1 - Diagram showing regimes of atmospheric and extra-atmospheric flight and depicting the jurisdictional boundary lines.

⁴ Jonathan C McDowell, ‘The Low Earth Orbit Satellite Population and Impacts of the SpaceX Starlink Constellation’ (2020) 892(2) *The Astrophysical Journal* L36, 2–3.

⁵ Alexandra Harris and Ray Harris, ‘The Need for Air Space and Outer Space Demarcation’ (2006) 22(1) *Space Policy* 3–4.

⁶ Convention for the Regulation of Aerial Navigation, opened for signature 13 October 1919, 7 LNTS 245 (entered into force 13 June 1922); Protocol of Amendment signed at Paris 17 February 1926, 26 LNTS 455 (entered into force 2 January 1927).

⁷ Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention), opened for signature 7 December 1944, 15 UNTS 295 (entered into force 4 April 1947).

Haley claimed that “the scientific and jurisprudential considerations determining the line are entirely realistic, identifiable, and sufficient.” This line is intended to be a demarcation between the aeronautic and astronautic regions and is located at approximately 275,000 feet (83.82km) above sea level. Haley asserts that the exact distance is subject to change as it is to be defined as *the point at which an aeronautical vehicle may no longer perform*, and where “airspace” therefore no longer exists.

To support his view on the importance of a scientific basis for the line of demarcation, Haley quotes Dr. C. Wilfred Jenks: “no lawyer should indulge in abstract speculation on the subject without first familiarizing himself with the scientific background.” Haley then draws on a 1958 article by Jean Rivoire and extrapolates that the best solution would be one which meets these four requirements: 1) it does not present an obstacle to progress, 2) it is in accordance with the fundamental principles of law and the latest scientific data, 3) it is clear, simple and elastic and 4) it is harmonious with the international agreements, conventions, and treaties that are in force. Haley believed the von Karman line satisfies each of these points.

Haley then compares flights taken by the X-2 and the X-15 rocket-powered craft, explaining that the former flew at an altitude where 98% of its weight was carried by aerodynamic lift, and only 2% by centrifugal force, thereby making it an aeronautic flight. The latter, however, which flew 7,274 km/h at an altitude of 108,000 feet at with virtually no aerodynamic lift, passed the von Karman line and thus qualified as a spacecraft. The constraints within the Mason and Gazley diagram on an aeronautic flight are therefore defined by velocity and altitude. Velocity is limited at 5000 feet per second at sea level, as beyond this point the skin temperature of the aircraft reaches upwards of 2000 degrees Fahrenheit, which is outside of the capability of contemporary materials and cooling technology. This velocity constraint, in turn, limits the reachable altitude of a pilot-driven aircraft at 150,000 feet. Haley stated that:⁸

Between these two barriers there is a corridor of continuous flight which terminates when at an approximate speed of 25,000 feet per second (7.62km/s) and an altitude of about 275,000 feet, the Kepler force takes over and the aerodynamic lift is gone. This is a critical jurisdictional line, marking the theoretical limit of air flight, which is here termed the von Karman line.

Haley correctly predicted that with advances in technology, this line would change slightly, but that it would remain relatively consistent, despite advances in technology, and expressed hope that lawyers and engineers would inevitably agree on an altitude where an aerodynamic vehicle could no longer function by generating lift.

2. A SURVEY OF MAJOR WRITERS' VIEWS

Haley catalogues other notable authors' opinions on the upper limit of sovereignty. Firstly, he looks at Prof. John Cobb Cooper, who examines the suggestion of basing the territory of a state on that state's ability to exercise its authority over it. Establishing that this would mean the power of rich states would give them a higher upper limit to sovereignty vis-à-vis poorer states, and asking:

Can we be said to live in such a world where the physical power at any one time of any particular state determines its international right to consider the region above its surface territories as part of its national territory?⁹

Haley cites Cooper's belief that with the application of this rule, every state, regardless of power or size, should have territorial rights that extend “as high as the rights of every other State, no matter how powerful. Cooper also suggests a three-zone concept of sovereignty: First, a zone that extends from the

⁸ Andrew G Haley, *Space Law and Government* (Appleton-Century-Crofts 1963) 98.

⁹ *Ibid*, 83.

ground to a height where aircraft, as now defined, can operate, wherein a subjacent state has full sovereignty. Second, a zone that extends up to 300 miles above the Earth's surface, where a subjacent state exercises sovereignty in tandem with the right of transit for all non-military flights. And third, a zone that extends infinitely above the second zone, which would be "free for the passage of all instrumentalities." Cooper ultimately points to the necessity of an international agreement with which Dr. Alex Meyer agrees, arguing the necessity of treating outer space as a "free area like the open seas".

Haley then contrasts two other viewpoints, first made by G. P. Zadorozhnij, who argues for setting the limit below the zone in which satellites orbit, and that of Dr. Ming-Min Peng, who would extend sovereignty to the limits of all flights until interplanetary flight was possible. To this point, another author, Dr. C. Wilfred Jenks, argues that the realities of interstellar space make it "a meaningless and dangerous abstraction" due to the scale of the universe.¹⁰ Oscar Schachter poses questions as to how the term "air" should be defined and to which point it extends, concluding thus: "whatever may be the precise boundary of the airspace, it is clear that when we go beyond it, we are legally in a no man's world". Haley then points to John A. Johnson, who claims that the interests of subjacent states would not be served by the extension of their sovereignty to extremely high altitudes and that a form of international control over specific space activities is required instead, by using as an example the circulation of satellites over all nations without permission or protest, he reasons that nations have not regarded territorial sovereignty as extending to the point at which satellite orbit has occurred.

Haley also refers to Dr. Eugene Pepin, C. E. S. Horford, who contends that space should be considered similarly as the high seas and Bin Cheng who offers a similar view, Haley suggests that these three disagree with extending sovereignty into space and would "...allow its free use above a certain line—perhaps the von Karman line". Next to be mentioned are, firstly, Stephen Gorove, who agrees that expansion of sovereignty into space is untenable, stating, however, that the most pressing problem is the establishment of an international inspection system; and secondly, Captain George D. Schrader, who supports the von Karman line and argues for the need for it to be accepted by the United States and Russia. To be concurrently regulated with the help of the IAF and the IISL and then submitted to the United Nations. Haley also quotes the ruling of the Supreme Court in *United States v. Causby*:¹¹

It is an ancient doctrine that a common law ownership of the land extended to the periphery of the universe — *Cujus est solum ejus est usque ad coelum*. But that doctrine has no place in the modern world.

Lastly, Haley addresses the dissenting opinion of William Strauss, who argues that there is no agreement on the scientific facts, and that "...the top of the "atmosphere" has been estimated at anywhere from 10 to 650 miles (16 to 1050 km) above the earth's surface". To this, Haley stresses that the issue is not with the facts, which are widely accepted, but with deciding which facts are relevant and how their importance should be factored in creating the jurisdictional line.

Thus far, Haley stresses the necessity of a scientific solution to the limit of sovereignty versus an arbitrary political one. Haley explains the dangers of a political solution and alludes to the reluctance of states to give up power as the reason behind the lack of progress in the determination of the upper limit. To exemplify this, most states formally forbid the passage of military aircraft of any kind over their territory at any height, despite this being impossible to control or enforce due to the vastness of space. Haley mentions a June 1959 report by the United Nations *ad hoc* Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), which deemed definitions of the upper limit to sovereignty to be premature,¹² and he quotes committee member George J. Feldman in the colloquium, stating that the

¹⁰ C Wilfred Jenks, 'International Law and Activities in Space' (1956) 5 *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 103, 103–04.

¹¹ *United States v. Causby*, 328 U.S. 256 (1946).

¹² United Nations Ad Hoc Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, 'Report of the Ad Hoc Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space' (June 1959) UN Doc A/4141E.

committee gave its approval to treating space as *res communis*.¹³ Haley's contemporary legal scholars, while torn on the exact point of termination of sovereignty, for the most were in agreement that "space", however that is to be defined, can either be *res communis* or *res nullius*, as those are the only practically possible solutions.

3. OTHER CRITIQUES TO THE VON KARMAN LINE

Haley points out that there are certain legal scholars who remained sceptical of the effectiveness of the Karman line since it does not create a definitive distinction between airspace and outer space. He responds to this claim by asserting that an approximate median may prove more beneficial than a rigid definition in many situations of ambiguity. Since there is an array of dynamic political, economic and military factors involved in the distinction between air law and space law, a purely spatial solution is purposeless.

3.1. *The Rocket Plane*

An objection that has been raised to the Von Karman line is that the delineation would be futile, given that there may be certain rocket-powered craft, such as the X-15, which will be able to travel to more than twice the altitude at which the aerodynamic lift subsides. Mr. Philip Quigg was the first to point out that such demarcation would not be practical if there were aircraft capable of coasting into the realm of satellites.¹⁴ He noted that the significance of such vehicles was that they obscured the distinction between air space and outer space. It is therefore clear that Mr. Quigg has adopted a more functional approach to the question of sovereignty, and his claims are rooted in the fact that there may be aircraft capable of travelling beyond the Karman line. Haley counters these propositions by stating that the X-15 is a rocket vehicle and not an aircraft; therefore, even if a functional definition is considered, the efficacy of the Karman line cannot be negated. He distinguishes between aircraft and spacecraft by outlining the technical, structural, and functional differences between the vehicles. An aircraft subsists on air and has not been designed to function in outer space, whereas a space vehicle does not subsist on air and merely uses air as a guidance aid on entry or departure. Although Mr. Quigg mentioned that the X-15 is a "winged craft and not a pure rocket", Haley counters this statement by asserting that the winged configuration does not determine whether it can be considered a rocket. Therefore, the existence of air guidance services does not necessarily mean that the vehicle is an aircraft. According to Haley, this would essentially imply that any object or vehicle which uses the Earth's air in any manner would not be a space vehicle. He argues as follows:

Under the assumptions of the Quigg approach, however, any vehicles – vehicles designed for earth orbiting or for voyages to the moon, the planets, and even the stars- would not be considered space vehicles if they used air guidance surfaces during the brief seconds of their departure from or return to the earth. Indeed, if they utilize the Earth's air in any fashion at all, it seems they would not be space vehicles.

3.2. *A Soviet Criticism*

The first full-scale treatise on space law, written by Feliks Nikolayevich Kovalev and Ivan Ivanovich Cheprov, dealt with certain aspects of the Karman Line.¹⁵ In Chapter 1 of the treatise, they criticize the Karman line as a means to determine the sphere of action of state sovereignty by means of coordinates of altitude and velocity. It is contended that the Karman line will be altered by alloys, and if a convertible airspace vehicle is created, the boundary would be "transformed into the most intricate and artful curve

¹³ Galloway, *The United Nations Ad Hoc Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space: Accomplishments and Implications for Legal Problems* (2d Colloq, Vienna, Springer-Verlag 1960) 30.

¹⁴ Philip W Quigg, 'Open Skies and Open Space' (October 1958) 37 *Foreign Affairs* 95–106.

¹⁵ FN Kovalev and II Cherpov, *Na puti k kosmicheskomu pravu* ['On the Path to Space Law'] (Izd-vo IMO, Moscow 1962).

with knots and loops”.¹⁶ The treatise notes that if there are foreign missiles and planes flying over a neutral state at the same altitude, the state could act against the former but not the latter. It is also argued that the Karman line does not consider actual flight possibilities. According to the authors, the Karman line also seems to ignore flight instrumentalities like ballistic missiles, which cannot be considered purely “transitional”.

Haley counters these claims by mentioning that the claims solely rely on the *1957 Masson-Gazley diagram*, which has been significantly altered and revised since then. He stated that the Karman line is a fixed horizontal line and is not represented by a curve as was claimed in the treatise. He also mentions that the boundary will change in due course of time with technological advancements and that it is impracticable that instrumentalities at the same altitude and geographical point can be considered to be in “airspace” and “cosmic space” simultaneously.

3.3. Alternative Approaches

Haley begins by noting that all satellites have at some point passed through the Karman line. Ballistic rockets and rocket-powered spacecraft are not constrained by aerodynamic lift support, which leads to an increased flight altitude. He concludes that only a very narrow corridor exists between air space and outer space. Essentially, there are three schemes of flight: the aviation regime, the corridor of atmospheric escape, and the astronautic regime. The aeronautical regime is regulated by the Chicago Convention, various other international laws, and domestic legislations, while the astronautic regime is ‘terra nullius’ or ‘no man’s land’. The primary question regards what regime can be made applicable to the escape corridor. Sanger was of the opinion that national jurisdiction should end at the beginning of the escape corridor. This can be compared with Dr. Cooper's idea of “contiguous zones”, in which there is a rite of passage to all non-military flights.¹⁷ However, a direct comparison cannot be drawn because Cooper’s upper limit was set at 300 miles, which would exclude a significant portion of the escape corridor.

Haley concedes that more research would be required before a conclusion can be reached with respect to whether direct control can be exercised for a limited stretch above the Karman line. Another approach to the problem was propounded by Eurico Fonseca, which is focused on the escape velocity of the vehicle as a determinant factor.¹⁸ Furthermore, G. Vernon Leopold and A.L. Scafuri have highlighted that the distinction is contingent on the demarcation between suborbital and orbital flight.¹⁹ Accordingly, it may be preferable to exempt vehicles from the territorial sovereignty of states, irrespective of the attained altitude, particularly when the eccentricity and angular momentum exceed the minimum threshold. However, if the momentum is reduced below the minimum threshold, they must be subject to national sovereignty of the underlying state.

4. CONTEMPORARY DEVELOPMENTS

4.1. Essential Features, Writers' Views, and Other Criticism

4.1.1. Technological development

From the perspective of technological development, many factors have increased the need for a legal demarcation of the upper limit to sovereignty. Firstly, the number of artificial satellites orbiting the Earth has increased tremendously, and there has been a downward trend in the altitude of those satellites in recent years. This is mostly due to the increased proportion of satellites in LEO, which now account

¹⁶ *Supra* note 8, 106.

¹⁷ See generally John Cobb Cooper and Ivan A Vlasic (eds), *Explorations in Aerospace Law: Selected Essays, 1946–1966* (McGill-Queen’s University Press, Montreal 1968).

¹⁸ See Eurico Sidónio Gouveia Xavier Lopes da Fonseca, *The Conquest of Space* (Lisbon: IMO, 1962).

¹⁹ G Vernon Leopold and AL Scafuri, ‘On the Boundary between Air Law and Space Law’ (abstract prepared for Andrew G Haley (ed), *Space Law and Government* (Appleton-Century-Crofts, New York 1963) 112).

for around 84% of orbiting satellites,²⁰ which, in turn, is mostly the result of satellite internet providers. Secondly, space is more important in general; there have now been numerous launches even outside of the Earth's orbit with various countries possessing this ability as opposed to only the USSR and the US, militaries of the world have developed or are actively developing various capabilities to de-orbit objects, and there are now LEO-orbiting Satellites capable of detailed imagery of subjacent nations at a resolution of less than 1 meter.²¹ Lastly, space travel has become accessible to the private sector, recently extending even to the tourist sector, which advertises travel to suborbital space using rocket-propelled aircraft.²²

However, the one factor that has still remained relatively constant is the capability of 'air breathing' aircraft. These have seemingly settled at a line that is significantly below the Haley suggested demarcation of 275,000 feet (~83km). The history of aircraft altitude progress can be seen in *Figure 1*, which should serve to ameliorate the concern of technological advance overcoming the von Karman line, at least with regards to "non-rocket" aircraft. That is because of the 3 evident facts: First, there is still a space of around 45 kilometers until we reach the originally defined von Karman line. Second, progress towards each subsequent kilometer proves more challenging, as can be observed by the flattening of the curve. Third, jet aircraft have not been able to progress a single kilometer higher in the last 45 years.²³

4.1.2. Jurisprudential development

While much progress has transpired in the 60 years following the publication of Andrew G. Haley's book, legal development has largely stagnated behind the technological. And this chapter, rather than representing a deviation, encapsulates the rule.

As for writing, a legal norm for the specific upper limit of sovereignty is yet to be established. That is despite the increasing importance of the issue during the progress of the space age, discussed below. Several nations have already used this lacuna to attempt to assert their sovereignty over outer space, such as the seven equatorial countries behind the *1976 Declaration of the First Meeting of Equatorial Countries on the Zone of the Geostationary Orbit* (Bogota Declaration),²⁴ mainly due to their strategic position below the geostationary orbit.²⁵ While the Bogota Declaration was of little consequence, perhaps a more important development is occurring in China and is best explained in the words of Mr. Phillip A. Meek in his address to the USCC:²⁶

From a legal perspective, the most troublesome indicators of China's apparent assertions of sovereignty in space are the increasing number of publications by influential Chinese authors advancing the principle that China's sovereign territory extends through outer space. As justification for the position, Chinese authors assert that their territorial claims to outer space are not inconsistent with international law because there is no internationally

²⁰ *Supra* note 4.

²¹ *Supra* note 5.

²² Debra Kamin, 'The Future of Space Tourism Is Now. Well, Not Quite' *The New York Times* (7 May 2022) <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/05/07/travel/space-travel-tourism.html>

²³ Rebecca Maksel, 'Who Holds the Altitude Record for an Airplane?' *Smithsonian Magazine* (2009) <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/air-space-magazine/who-holds-the-altitude-record-for-an-airplane-141522931/>

²⁴ Declaration of the First Meeting of Equatorial Countries on the Zone of the Geostationary Orbit ('Bogotá Declaration') (Bogotá, 8 November 1976) 15 ILM 493 (1976).

²⁵ Lawrence D Roberts, 'A Lost Connection: Geostationary Satellite Networks and the International Telecommunication Union' (2000) 15 Berk Tech LJ 1095.

²⁶ Phillip A Meek, 'Testimony Before the US-China Economic and Security Review Commission: China's Views of Sovereignty and Methods of Access Control' (Testimony, US-China Economic and Security Review Commission, 2018).

accepted definition of outer space that has a demarcation point at which national airspace ends, and outer space begins.

The year 1967 marked the ratification of the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, opened for signature* (OST), which among other things, established space as *res communis*.²⁷ Thus, proving the majority of the authors discussed in Haley's book correct and casting away the more fringe theories of sovereignty '*ad coelum*'. However, the OST fell short of defining the point at which this demarcation between airspace and space happens. The U.S. FAA and NASA use a 50-mile limit,²⁸ whereas international regulatory agencies such as the FAI,²⁹ the U.S. Air Force and Space Force, as well as the governments of Denmark, Australia, and Kazakhstan, through their respective space legislations, have established the limit at 100km.³⁰ In some of these cases, this 100km limit is termed the von Karman line.

The author Thomas Gangale, in his article 'The Non-Karman Line: An Urban Legend of the Space Age', doubts the validity of the origin of this jurisdictional line, as well as its calculation. According to Gangale, Haley himself frequently and substantially changed not only the distance to the line itself, but also the methodology describing the line, basing it on various unrelated physical phenomena. Gangale suggests that since von Karman had numerous contemporaries whose own interpretations of a boundary were more closely matched with the now accepted 100km, it is not merely unreasonable to attribute it to von Karman, but in doing so, perhaps unintentionally it uses the famous aerodynamicist to attribute a "scientific basis" to a political concept.³¹ Gangale also discusses a lack of any proof that Theodore von Karman ever worked on such a calculation.³²

The aerospace engineer Nicolas Bérend focused in his work on finding the 'missing calculation' behind the von Karman line and suggested that Haley may have merely received the diagram from von Karman, without any explanation. Bérend also calls attention to numerous apparent points of confusion of the underlying physics.³³ The astrophysicist Jonathan McDowell further investigates the basis of the 100km "von Karman line" and referring to the FAI document '*100 km Altitude Boundary for Astronautics*' he states: "it is unfortunate that discussion in this official document in the section 'demonstration of usefulness of Karman line' appears to be poorly researched".³⁴ McDowell thereafter establishes that the induction by which the FAI came to the 100km's, if applied correctly, would lead to an 80km Karman Line instead. Following the publication of this article by McDowell, the FAI released a statement on its von Karman page, acknowledging the research (though not explicitly), and proposing an international workshop in 2019.³⁵ However, no further updates have been given on the page since.

²⁷ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, opened for signature 27 January 1967, 610 UNTS 205 (entered into force 10 October 1967).

²⁸ Thomas Gangale, 'The Non Karman Line: An Urban Legend of the Space Age' (2017) 41 Journal of Space Law 151, 152-155.

²⁹ S Sanz Fernández de Córdoba, '100 km Altitude Boundary for Astronautics' (Fédération Aéronautique Internationale, 2004) <https://www.fai.org/page/icare-boundary>

³⁰ Anon, 'Near Space: The Quest for a New Legal Frontier' (2021) 13 International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety, 2.

³¹ *Supra* note 21, 159-62, 177.

³² *Supra* note 21, 167.

³³ Nicolas Bérend, 'The Missing Calculation behind the Original Kármán Line Definition – A Credible Hypothesis' in Proceedings of the *International Astronautical Congress 2021* (Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2021) 2-4.

³⁴ Jonathan C McDowell, 'The Edge of Space: Revisiting the Kármán Line' (2018) 151 Acta Astronautica 668, 3.

³⁵ Anon, 'Statement about the Kármán Line' (Fédération Aéronautique Internationale, 2018) <https://www.fai.org/news/statement-about-karman-line> accessed 10 May 2022.

4.2. Alternative Approaches

Haley suggests numerous alternative approaches to the issue of jurisdiction. Some of these approaches will be analyzed in line with the various technological and scientific developments that have taken place since his book was written.

To some extent, Professor Gangale countered the approach taken by Haley in his book “*How High the Sky? The Definition and Delimitation of Outer Space and Territorial Airspace in International Law*”.³⁶ Gangale acknowledges two main approaches to the question of limiting sovereignty. Firstly, a spatial approach which sets a specific altitude, delineating where sovereign airspace ends and where outer space begins. Secondly, a functional approach by which space law is deemed to be applicable based on the activities that are conducted, regardless of where these activities occur. Haley and Gangale do not diverge on this point. Gangale does, however, highlight the immediacy of the need to answer the question of delimitation, especially given that private space flight and suborbital transportation are on the rise. He holds that the *ad coelum* doctrine is untenable because space vehicles may travel from one superjacent area to another, and the rotation of the Earth makes it difficult to create a vertical upper limit. Later, the *ad coelum* doctrine was overruled, and space was considered to be the common heritage of mankind.

Apart from the Karman line, there have been other approaches to determine a vertical limit to national sovereignty.

4.2.1. The political approach

Gangale notes that sovereignty is distinguishable from independence and control,³⁷ with the latter being essentially a subset of sovereignty. Every state has the right to exercise exclusive control over activities that take place in its airspace.³⁸ The effective control theory is a political theory; however, it is pertinent to note that it is purely conceptual because no altitude of control has ever been proposed.

According to the state interest theory, the limits of sovereignty extend until the point at which state interest exists. Therefore, state interests would logically end at the uppermost limits of the atmosphere.³⁹ The interest theory is closely related to the test of effective control since states normally exercise control over territory that they have an interest in.

4.2.2. The spatial approach

As the name suggests, the spatial approach proposes a delineation on the basis of a specified boundary at a defined altitude. This approach does not take into consideration the types of activities that are carried out in air space or outer space. There are three different arguments within this approach: the technical argument, the arbitrary argument, and the combined approach. An arbitrary single boundary is a 12 nautical mile limit of vertical sovereignty, similar to the territorial sea model. The problem with this approach is that certain states may have the technical capabilities to operate beyond the arbitrary single boundary. Additionally, the role of physical phenomena such as gravitational pull, escape velocity and atmospheric physics on the spatial approach cannot be ignored. Bin Cheng has noted as follows:⁴⁰

³⁶ Thomas Gangale, *How High the Sky?: The Definition and Delimitation of Outer Space and Territorial Airspace in International Law* (Leiden: Brill Nijhoff 2018).

³⁷ *Ibid*, 32.

³⁸ Hans Kelsen, *General Theory of Law and State* (Routledge, London 1945).

³⁹ JFL Nijeholt, *Air Sovereignty* (1st edn, Springer Science Dordrecht 1910) 46.

⁴⁰ Bin Cheng, *Recent Developments in Air Law* (Vol 12, 1956) 208.

Airspace is the entire space where air is to be found under any form. This is identical with the atmosphere in its broadest meaning, including all of its layers, irrespective of whether it is sufficiently dense to carry aircraft.

Beyond these conventional approaches, certain scholars have even suggested a variable 30-statute mile limit during times of peace and a 4030-statute mile limit during times of war.⁴¹

There has also been an attempt to define the region above and adjacent to national airspace as “near space” extending 18 km above sea level to 160 km above sea level (International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety 2020:10).⁴² This approach takes inspiration from the demarcation provided under UNCLOS by which the continental shelf, contiguous zone and exclusive economic zone were created to protect the safety and security of the coastal state and also to prevent exploitation of economic resources in the adjacent areas to the territorial waters. Near space is not considered to be a part of the national territory of the state, however, there are certain restrictions that are placed on other states operating in this area. While there is a right to innocent passage for civil and commercial activities, there is a right of the underlying state to utilize and administer the near space to the exclusion of other states.⁴³

4.2.3. Functional approach

The functional approach focuses on the activities that are conducted in outer space to better understand the jurisdictional scope of space law. It must be noted that the security interests of states and the right to self-defense are inextricably intertwined with the functional approach. Lipson and Katzenbach have asserted that all states must have the unfettered right to exercise jurisdiction over military satellites and space vehicles in their superjacent airspace, while also ensuring that the right to free passage of other non-military satellites and vehicles is protected.⁴⁴ Thus, proponents of the functional approach do not advocate in favor of demarcation but argue that jurisdictional concerns are correlated to the purposes for which the vehicle or object is used. There is a general consensus that certain activities (testing nuclear weapons, changing the composition of outer space, establishing military bases, etc.) must not be permitted. However, the primary issue with this approach is the failure to establish a reasonable standard of what constitutes a “space activity”. The only definition that can be reached is that all launches into outer space, as well as any other ancillary activities conducted while the vehicle is in outer space, may be considered space activities.

4.2.4. Gangale’s approach

Gangale’s approach appears to be a coalescence of various other approaches. He alludes to a “conventional solution” by which states must engage in negotiations to draft an international legal instrument that delineates between air law and space law rather than giving effect to any conceptual principle. Owing to the complexity of technological and scientific criteria, a practical solution to resolve the persisting issue is for states to arrive at a mutual agreement. Without a clear definition, there may be conflict regarding the allocation of positions in geostationary orbits and other associated issues like the uniform aerospace regime.

Another solution that he refers to is what he calls a “hybrid solution”. There are two primary questions which must be answered then: where does outer space begin, and where does spatial sovereignty end? Both questions must be determined separately. A consensus seems to have been reached in terms of determining the lower limit of space law. It is clear that international space law applies to any satellite that orbits around the Earth; hence, logically, space law must begin at the lowest possible altitude at

⁴¹ Lipson L and Katzenbach N, *Außen Politik. Zeitschrift für Internationale Fragen* vol 8 (1961) 43.

⁴² International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety, ‘Near Space: The Quest for a New Legal Frontier’ (2020) 13, 10.

⁴³ *Ibid*, 11.

⁴⁴ See *supra* note 34.

which a satellite can stay in orbit. Thus, airspace sovereignty cannot extend beyond this lower limit, i.e. beyond the lowest point at which a satellite is capable of remaining in orbit. Earlier, one of the criticisms of this theory was that it would be difficult to monitor the altitude of satellites at a given point of time, however, this has been resolved with the advent of global navigation satellite system technology.

The lower limit or “lowest perigee theory” has a direct impact on the right to free access to outer space and will therefore affect the upper limit of state sovereignty. Security threats and increased military activities in outer space are also determinant criteria in settling the upper limit. It remains to be seen whether a feasible solution can be reached that resolves the trade-off between security concerns and the right to free passage. However, since all space objects travel through the atmosphere upon their return, there is a need to differentiate between air law and space law on the basis of the intended function of the vehicle.

5. CONCLUSION

The subject matter of a vertical limit to sovereignty has been extensively studied and analyzed by legal scholars and scientists, who have created an impressive array of approaches. Unfortunately, despite the ever-increasing need for the upper limit of sovereignty to be formally defined, it currently still remains undefined in international law. There are, however, two points of consolation. Firstly, the OST, which is now widely considered customary international law, at least establishes that wherever space begins, state sovereignty ends. Concurrently, the most widely used point to refer to where space begins seems to be at 100km. Secondly, the lack of state disputes over satellite orbits superjacent to their territory may suggest yet another custom in formation. For these reasons, it seems superfluous to these authors to give any further recommendations at this time.